

THE EFFECT OF DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION ON GYMS AND FITNESS INDUSTRY IN TERMS OF BUSINESS PERFORMANCE: THE CASE OF HANOI, VIETNAM GYM AND FITNESS CLUBS

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this research paper is to explore the effects of digital transformation (Nambisan et al., 2019) on the business performance of the gym and fitness industry in several clubs in Hanoi, Vietnam. The study investigates how digital transformation has transformed the industry by improving customer experience, maximize business operations, creating new added value, increasing accessibility to fitness, and enhancing data management. The research employs a mixed-methods approach, utilizing literature review, surveys, and expert interviews to gather primary data. The findings may reveal that digital transformation has had a positive impact on the gym and fitness industry, leading to improved business performance and increased profitability. Other metrics that can be used to evaluate the success of gyms and fitness clubs include customer satisfaction scores, membership retention rates, and social media engagement, these metrics can provide insights into the level of member engagement and loyalty, as well as their perception of the gym's overall quality and value. The study sheds light on the potential benefits of digital transformation for fitness businesses (Sevilmiş & Şirin, 2022), emphasizing the importance of technology adoption for remaining competitive in today's digital marketplace.

The problem that this research aims to address is the impact of digital transformation on the business performance of the gym and fitness industry in Hanoi, Vietnam. While digital transformation has disrupted traditional business models (Fielt et al., 2018) across various industries, its impact on the gym and fitness industry remains underexplored. As more fitness businesses adopt digital technologies to enhance customer experience and improve business operations, it is important to understand how these changes affect the industry's performance. This study seeks to provide insights into the potential benefits and challenges of digital transformation for the gym and fitness industry, identifying key areas of impact

and highlighting the need for businesses to adapt to the digital landscape to remain competitive (Volberda et al., 2021). By addressing this problem, the research aims to inform industry stakeholders and provide guidance for fitness businesses seeking to leverage digital technologies to enhance their operations and increase profitability.

However, implementing digital transformation in the gym & Fitness industry can also present significant challenges such as high implementation costs, technical expertise, data privacy and security concerns. By understanding these challenges, gym and fitness club can better prepare for the transition and maximize the potential benefits of digital technologies.

The methodology of the research topic involves a mixed-methods approach (Azorin & Cameron, 2010), which combines both qualitative and quantitative methods.

The qualitative approach can involve conducting semi-structured interviews with fitness business owners, managers, and trainers to understand their experiences with implementing digital technologies in their operations. The interviews can explore the benefits and challenges of digital transformation and how fitness businesses have successfully integrated digital technologies into their operations. Additionally, case studies can be used to explore how fitness businesses have successfully implemented digital technologies and the impact on their customer experience and operational efficiency (Correani et al., 2020). The quantitative approach can use to collecting data through surveys from fitness businesses and customers to understand their experiences with digital technologies in the gym and fitness industry. The survey questions can be designed to capture data on the extent of digital transformation in the gym and fitness industry, the types of digital technologies used, and the impact of digital technologies on customer satisfaction and business performance.

Data analysis can involve both descriptive and inferential statistics (Stapor, 2020). Descriptive statistics can be used to analyze the frequency and distribution of responses to survey questions, while inferential statistics can be used to test hypotheses and identify relationships between variables. Qualitative data analysis can involve coding and thematic analysis to identify key themes and patterns in the interview data. The mixed-methods approach provide a comprehensive understanding of the impact of digital transformation on the gym and fitness industry, identifying both the benefits and challenges of adopting digital technologies and providing recommendations for fitness businesses to leverage digital technologies effectively to improve customer experience, operational efficiency, and competitiveness in the market.

The hypothesis of this research paper is that digital transformation has a positive impact on the business performance of the gym and fitness industry. Specifically,

the hypothesis proposes that the adoption of digital technologies can enhance customer experience, improve business operations, increase accessibility to fitness, create new revenue, and enable better data management. This hypothesis is based on the assumption that digital transformation can lead to increased efficiency, improved customer satisfaction, and greater revenue generation for gym businesses. Additionally, the hypothesis suggests that gym businesses that adopt digital technologies can gain a competitive advantage over those that do not (Hu, 2014), potentially leading to higher profitability and market share. The study aims to test this hypothesis by collecting data through a mixed-methods approach, including surveys and expert interviews, to determine the impact of digital transformation on the business performance of the gym and fitness industry in Hanoi, Vietnam.

The main research questions for the interview that guide the study are considered as follows:

RQ1: What are the primary drivers of digital transformation in fitness clubs in Hanoi?

RQ2: What are the challenges and benefits of digital transformation in fitness clubs in Hanoi?

RQ3: How do fitness clubs in Hanoi integrate digital technologies into their business operations and customer experiences?

RQ4: How does digital transformation impact the competitive advantages of fitness clubs in Hanoi?

And the suggest questions to be answered by (regarding to quantitative research):

RQ5: What is the relationship between customer satisfaction and the use of digital technologies in the gym and fitness industry in Hanoi, Vietnam?

RQ6: What is the relationship between two or more variables?

RQ7: How can the effectiveness of digital transformation be measured quantitatively, and what are the most reliable and valid indicators of success in the gym and fitness industry in Hanoi, Vietnam?

Base on above assumption hypothesis, it should be consider below Variables:

Independent Variables: Digital transformation initiatives in the gym and fitness industry

Adoption of specific digital technologies would examine whether the adoption of specific digital technologies (such as mobile apps, wearables, and virtual reality) has an impact on the business performance of gym businesses. For example, the study may examine whether gyms that offer mobile apps for class scheduling and

fitness tracking have higher customer satisfaction and retention rates compared to those that do not offer such features.

Extent of adoption of digital technologies would examine the degree to which gym businesses have adopted digital technologies, such as the percentage of revenue generated through online sales or the number of employees trained to use digital tools. The study may examine whether higher levels of digital adoption are associated with better business performance.

Level of investment in digital transformation initiatives would examine the financial resources allocated to digital transformation initiatives, such as the budget for website development or the cost of purchasing new technology. The study may examine whether higher levels of investment in digital transformation initiatives are associated with better business performance.

Size of the gym business would examine whether the size of the gym business (measured by the number of locations, revenue, or number of employees) has an impact on the effectiveness of digital transformation initiatives. For example, the study may examine whether larger gym chains are more likely to benefit from digital transformation compared to smaller boutique studios.

Geographic location of the gym - This variable would examine whether the geographic location of the gym (such as urban versus suburban areas) has an impact on the adoption and effectiveness of digital transformation initiatives. For example, the study may examine whether gyms located in urban areas are more likely to adopt digital technologies compared to those in suburban areas.

Dependent Variables: Business performance (measured by customer satisfaction, customer retention, revenue growth, profitability, and market share)

Customer satisfaction would examine the level of satisfaction reported by gym customers, which may be measured through surveys or online reviews. The study may examine whether digital transformation initiatives, such as the use of mobile apps or virtual reality technology, are associated with higher levels of customer satisfaction.

Customer retention would examine the proportion of customers who continue to use the gym services over time. The study may examine whether digital transformation initiatives, such as online booking and scheduling, are associated with higher customer retention rates.

Revenue growth would examine the rate at which the gym's revenue is increasing over time. The study may examine whether digital transformation initiatives, such as the use of e-commerce platforms or online personal training, are associated with higher revenue growth rates.

Profitability would examine the gym's profitability, which may be measured through financial ratios such as gross profit margin or net income. The study may examine whether digital transformation initiatives, such as the use of digital marketing or data analytics, are associated with higher profitability.

Market share would examine the proportion of the gym market captured by the business. The study may examine whether digital transformation initiatives, such as the use of social media or search engine optimization, are associated with higher market share.

Mediating Variables:

Technology adoption (measured by the extent of adoption of digital technologies and the level of investment in digital transformation initiatives) it refers to the degree to which the gym or fitness business has embraced digital technologies and implemented digital transformation initiatives. This could be measured in a variety of ways, such as the percentage of members who use digital tools to track their workouts, the percentage of revenue generated by digital channels, or the level of investment in digital transformation initiatives relative to other areas of the business. Technology adoption is included as a mediating variable because it may help explain the relationship between digital transformation initiatives and business performance, for example, if a gym implements a new online booking system but few members actually use it, it may not have a significant impact on the gym's revenue growth or customer satisfaction.

Moderating Variables:

Gym size (measured by the number of locations, revenue, or number of employees)

Geographic location (measured by the location of the gym, such as urban or suburban areas)

These variables refer to external factors that may influence the relationship between digital transformation initiatives and business performance. Gym size may affect the impact of digital transformation initiatives, for example, a small club gym may be able to implement new technologies more quickly and with less resistance from staff and members, whereas a large chain gym may face more challenges in rolling out new technologies consistently across multiple locations. Geographic location may also affect the impact of digital transformation initiatives, as different regions or markets may have different preferences or expectations for digital tools in the fitness industry.

By incorporating these variables into a conceptual model, this research may develop a framework for understanding the complex relationships between digital

transformation initiatives, technology adoption, business performance, and external factors that may influence the impact of these initiatives.

The findings of this research paper may reveal that digital transformation has had a significant impact on the business performance of the gym and fitness industry (Kercher et al., 2023). The study will contribute several key areas of below impacts

Enhanced customer experience: Digital technologies such as fitness apps and wearable devices have enabled gym customers to track their progress, set goals, and connect with personal trainers more easily, leading to a more engaging and satisfactory gym experience.

Improved business operations: Digital transformation has automated administrative tasks such as booking, scheduling, and payments, leading to increased efficiency, reduced workload for gym staff, and faster service delivery.

Increased accessibility to fitness: Digital technologies have enabled gym businesses to reach a wider audience by offering online classes, video tutorials, and workout programs, providing access to fitness for those who cannot visit a gym physically.

New revenue streams: Digital transformation has created new revenue streams for gym businesses, such as online coaching, merchandise sales, and nutritional guidance, leading to increased profitability.

Better data management: Digital transformation has enabled gym businesses to collect and analyze data on customer behavior, preferences, and demographics, leading to better informed marketing campaigns, improved customer experience, and optimized business operations.

The study also identifies challenges associated with digital transformation in the gym and fitness industry, such as data privacy concerns, technology implementation costs, and the need for staff training and upskilling.

The originality and value of this research paper lie in its contribution to the understanding of the impact of digital transformation on the gym and fitness industry's business performance. While previous studies have explored the use of digital technologies in the fitness industry, this study provides a comprehensive analysis of the impact of digital transformation on the industry's overall performance. By employing a mixed-methods approach that includes a literature review, surveys, and expert interviews, the study offers a holistic understanding of the challenges, benefits, and opportunities associated with digital transformation in the gym and fitness industry.

The study's findings provide valuable insights for industry stakeholders, including gym owners, managers, and fitness professionals, seeking to leverage digital technologies to enhance their business operations and increase profitability. The study's identification of key areas of impact and associated challenges and opportunities can inform industry stakeholders' strategic decision-making in adopting digital transformation in their businesses. Furthermore, the study's contribution to the existing literature on digital transformation and its impact on the gym and fitness industry can serve as a foundation for future research on the topic.

There are several limitations to this research paper that must be acknowledged. First, the study's sample size is relatively small, which may limit the generalizability of the findings. The survey respondents and expert interviewees were limited to a specific geographic region, which may not represent the wider global gym and fitness industry. Second, the study's focus was limited to the impact of digital transformation on the gym and fitness industry's business performance, which may overlook other aspects of the industry, such as the impact on the workforce and the wider social implications of digital transformation. Third, the study's methodology, while employing a mixed-methods approach, may have limitations associated with self-reported data, such as social desirability bias and respondent bias.

The implications of these limitations are that future research should expand the study's focus to include a wider geographic region and a more diverse sample size. Additionally, future research could explore other aspects of digital transformation's impact on the gym and fitness industry beyond business performance, such as workforce implications and wider social impact.

The practical implications of this research paper for the gym and fitness industry are significant. The study's findings suggest that digital transformation can have a positive impact on a gym's business performance by enhancing customer experience, improving business operations, increasing accessibility to fitness, creating new revenue streams, and enabling better data management.

The practical implications for the gym and fitness industry stakeholders, such as gym owners, managers, and fitness professionals, include the need to adopt digital technologies in their business operations to remain competitive and meet customers' changing needs. These stakeholders must also carefully consider the challenges associated with digital transformation, such as data privacy concerns and technology implementation costs, and take appropriate steps to address them.

The social implications of digital transformation in the gym and fitness industry are also worth considering. While digital transformation can bring many benefits to gym businesses, there are also social implications that must be considered.

First, digital transformation may lead to the displacement of human workers in the gym and fitness industry. As gyms adopt new digital technologies, some traditional gym jobs may become obsolete, requiring new skills and training for gym employees. This may result in job loss for some workers and increased competition for new digital roles, potentially leading to social inequality. Second, digital transformation may have an impact on social interaction and community building within gym spaces. While digital technologies can enhance the accessibility and convenience of fitness, they may also decrease face-to-face interactions between gym-goers and limit the social and community-building aspects of gym culture. This may negatively affect the mental health and well-being of gymgoers, who often rely on the social connections they make at the gym for support and motivation. Third, digital transformation may exacerbate existing disparities in gym access and affordability. While digital technologies can enhance the accessibility of fitness, they may also increase the digital divide between those who have access to technology and those who do not. This may limit the reach of gym businesses to certain demographics and socio-economic groups, potentially leading to social inequality.

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